

IMAGINE

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IMAGINARY:
THE EROSION OF THE LONG-STANDING
REPUBLICAN TRADITION**

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Abstract: The French imaginary is a Republican imaginary that is premised on political liberty. The red thread across the political thought and the various constitutions of France has been the pursuit of the ideal political regime that would best realise political liberty and the general interest. That approach stands in stark contrast with the civil-liberty-focused Anglo-Saxon liberal tradition according to which state power ought to be curtailed in order to maximise individual rights. Those two essentially different traditions could rather peacefully coexist at the Westphalian time of the nation-states. The clash has however become inevitable in a time where globalisation and the latter's regional avatars, such as the European Union, act as vehicles of Anglo-Saxon liberalism. This paper introduces to the French constitutional imaginary relying on the tools provided by intellectual history and constitutional law. It contrasts it with the Anglo-Saxon political thought and shows how the former remains strong despite the erosion caused by the pervasiveness of the latter.

KEYWORDS: Republicanism; Liberalism; Concept of liberty; French political tradition; Constitutionalism

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On the French constitutional imaginary :

The erosion of the long-standing Republican tradition

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Abstract

The French imaginary is a Republican imaginary that is premised on political liberty. The red thread across the political thought and the various constitutions of France has been the pursuit of the ideal political regime that would best realise political liberty and the general interest. That approach stands in stark contrast with the civil-liberty-focused Anglo-Saxon liberal tradition according to which state power ought to be curtailed in order to maximise individual rights. Those two essentially different traditions could rather peacefully coexist at the Westphalian time of the nation-states. The clash has however become inevitable in a time where globalisation and the latter's regional avatars, such as the European Union, act as vehicles of Anglo-Saxon liberalism. This paper introduces to the French constitutional imaginary relying on the tools provided by intellectual history and constitutional law. It contrasts it with the Anglo-Saxon political thought and shows how the former remains strong despite the erosion caused by the pervasiveness of the latter.

Introduction

It is somewhat paradoxical nowadays to reflect on collective imaginaries at a time of individualism, post-nationalism and transnational governance. It is even more paradoxical to reflect on such imaginaries with a national key. Examining national imaginaries indeed entails looking at idiosyncrasies, that is those specific, unique, unparalleled features of a given national community that distinguish the latter

from other national communities. Such type of emotions-based idiosyncrasies may – understandably – be perceived with suspicion in the context of European integration as a reason-based, unity-driven political project.

First, idiosyncrasies are rooted in the past and in the mental representations inherited therefrom while current times primarily value the present and, to some extent, the future. Second, national traits may be a reason for pride for those sharing them (and for prejudice for those who do not). They are based on a supposedly pre-existing and mysterious ‘We, the People’ and create a sense of kinship, a feeling of national exceptionalism that may ultimately turn into sheer nationalism and oppose political communities against one another.

Third and in connection with the previous item, those idiosyncrasies appear more subjective than objective inasmuch as they are the result of collective imaginaries, no matter they are specifically called ‘imagined communities’, ‘imagined structures of belief’ or ‘invented traditions’.¹ Those imaginaries refer to a certain mythical past that has more to do with collective memory than scientific historicity. With their inherent dreamlike component, imaginaries bear a degree of irrationality and can therefore fuel potentially fateful passions when giving rise to political claims. Fourth and final, on a certain predominant reading of constitutionalism nowadays, constitutional idiosyncrasies in particular may appear as a contradiction in terms. It is indeed often assumed in Europe – and more broadly in the Western world – that constitutionalism refers to universal, individual-based values (often under the banner of ‘liberal constitutionalism’ or ‘liberal democracy’) as opposed to community values defined along national lines.

Such partial approach to constitutionalism appears to overlook the latter’s density and, in particular, the actual constitutions in their political, cultural and symbolic

¹ See, respectively, Benedict Anderson, *Imagined Communities: Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism*, Verso, revised edition, 2016; Paul W. Kahn, *Political Theology: Four New Chapters on the Concept of Sovereignty*, Columbia University Press, 2012; Eric Hobsbawm, Terence Ranger, *The Invention of Tradition*, Cambridge University Press, 2012.

dimensions. A research project such as the one undertaken by Jan Komárek is thus all the more welcome despite the few eyebrows it may raise. Researching on collective imaginaries is arguably quite politically incorrect nowadays, especially when those imaginaries are examined along national lines. Such type of research is indeed premised on an introspective and backward-looking interest into kinship, group psychology and self-perception. Worse, its outcomes might be instrumental in buttressing nationalistic aspirations in a post-national Europe.

Although such type of research project undoubtedly runs against the individualistic tide embodied, *inter alia*, by the European Union and the system established by the European Convention on Human Rights (hereinafter ‘the ECHR’), exploring national constitutional imaginaries in Europe remains indispensable to further the understanding of European constitutionalism. Against that background, the examination of the French constitutional imaginary cannot be missing within a research project that aims at mapping national constitutional imaginaries and confronting them with European integration. The distinctive and unique imaginary that France has forged over the centuries appears a most suitable case-study to understand both the construction of national imaginaries in Europe but also the challenges that EU integration, with its own concepts, narratives and values, represent for those imaginaries.

The French imaginary has generated its own political and social model. The self-perceived exceptionalism is indeed not confined to the United States. That feeling of uniqueness inherited from the French Revolution is entrenched in the Great Nation. Not only has it induced the widespread belief that France has something to say to the world, but it also largely explains France’s past as a colonial power yearning to share its model with other peoples as part of the ‘civilising mission’ of European states, often referred to in the English language as the ‘white man’s burden’. The French constitutional imaginary is therefore worth examining as a domestic product but also as an export product that travelled, together with the political model underpinning it, to French ex-colonies and to those former

communist states in Europe where the French revolutionary ideals have inspired the Russian Revolution and thus shaped the own imaginary of those states.

The content of the French imaginary is quite unique. As will be explained further, it significantly differs from the currently prevailing ideological aspirations promoted by globalisation in general and European integration in particular. While the French imaginary is a Republican imaginary that relies on distinctive concepts that cannot always be grasped, despite their use in other languages and cultures, by those who are not familiar with that specific instance of imaginary (such as citizenship, the Nation, the general interest, sovereignty or the constituent power), the EU strives on neoliberalism, the rule of law, fundamental rights and more broadly liberal constitutionalism and individualism, that is on values that are commonly associated with another type of constitutional imaginary: Anglo-Saxon liberalism.

Accordingly, France's belonging to the European Union and to the ECHR system as vehicles of Anglo-Saxon liberalism was likely to put to the test and even undermine the French constitutional imaginary. This paper aims at examining to what extent the latter intuition is correct. As long as those two quite type of different imaginaries, the French and the Anglo-Saxon, could live their lives autonomously without too much regard for one another on a daily basis, it is submitted that their radical differences would not raise any major issue. Frictions however appear inevitable where they start getting in touch with one another. Constitutional imaginaries are like tectonic plates: they can have a smooth coexistence provided they stay apart but, where certain factors lead them to collide, the disruption can be immense. That is arguably the case on the fertile ground offered by European integration as the most successful regional experiment of globalisation. The claim of this paper is that the French powerful and long-standing Republican imaginary is being eroded by the Anglo-Saxon imaginary through globalisation in general and European integration in particular. The French constitutional imaginary, which is deeply engrained within the collective psyche, has indeed been significantly destabilised by the liberal political and legal

developments induced by the belonging of France to the European Union and more generally by globalisation and the correlative rise of individualism and human rights.

Against that background, this paper explores the French constitutional imaginary, its construction, specific content and evolution in the mirror-inverted light of the Anglo-Saxon liberal imaginary that permeates European integration. The first section of this paper addresses a preliminary issue of a methodological nature: what are the available tools to determine the past and current content of the constitutional imaginary of a given community? On that basis, the second section teases out, in contrast with the Anglo-Saxon imaginary, the fundamentals of the French imaginary as a Republican imaginary resting on specific approaches to liberty, the constitution, public power and society. It shows in particular how embedded that imaginary has been in French intellectual history so that even French liberal authors have themselves developed a unique political thought that is far from being purely liberal. The third section subsequently addresses the liberal, Anglo-Saxon shift prompted by globalisation and European integration from the seventies onwards and how it has translated into constitutional law. The fourth section looks at major political moments that bring to light and confirm, in reaction to Anglo-Saxon liberal tremors, the embeddedness of the French Republican imaginary within the French population. Finally, the conclusion recaps the main findings and addresses the issue as to whether the Republican imaginary can ever be replaced by an Anglo-Saxon type of liberal imaginary.

1. How can we know about constitutional imaginaries?

Determining the content of the French constitutional imaginary requires in the first place to understand what a constitutional imaginary is, what function it fulfils

within a society and how it relates to power and the law.² It is on the basis of that broad understanding of constitutional imaginaries in general that it becomes possible to come up with appropriate heuristic tools that allow to grasp the content of specific imaginaries.

Collective imaginaries as social artefacts

Constitutional imaginaries are a subcategory of collective imaginaries, which are themselves social artefacts. Collective imaginaries have little to do with scientific historicity. Because they are socially constructed, they primarily derive from (selective) memory, psychology or sociology. They consist in uniting myths whose function is to create a comforting feeling of kinship connecting the dead and the living. Truth does not matter as far as collective imaginaries are concerned. It does not matter indeed whether their subjective, memory-based content is in line with their objective, history-based content. Since they imply the idealisation and, often, the extrapolation of given community features, collective imaginaries are actually bound to be erroneous or partial without that being an issue in itself. What matters instead with collective imaginaries is that they manage to fulfil their herding function: building a community feeling, a 'We' distinct from others that can subsequently develop political aspirations to self-rule as 'We, the people'.

Nations are arguably the most successful and long-lasting collective imaginaries that have ever been conceived of by human mind. National imaginaries, often branded as 'national identity', are a made-up, subjective construct based on objective elements that have been sorted and ranked on the basis of their respective weights, those weights being themselves determined according to given criteria and preferences. In his influential lecture on the concept of the nation delivered at the Sorbonne in 1882,³ French intellectual Ernest Renan explained

² On constitutional imaginaries (or imagination), see eg Martin Loughlin, 'The Constitutional Imagination' (2015) 78 *Modern Law Review* 1, p. 1; Paul Blokker, 'Populism; constituent power and constitutional imagination', in Martin Belov (ed.), *Populist Constitutionalism and Illiberal Democracies: Between Constitutional Imagination, Normative Entrenchment and Political Reality*, Intersentia, 2021, pp. 149-170.

³ Ernest Renan, *What Is a Nation? And Other Political Writings*, Columbia University Press, 2018, pp. 247-263.

that a nation was characterised by ‘a rich legacy of memories’ and by ‘the desire to live together, the desire to continue to invest in the heritage that we have jointly received’. According to him, there would be no nation without ‘forgetting’ since ‘the essence of a nation is that all individuals have many things in common and also that they have forgotten many things’. Nations and national identity, as any other collective imaginary, thus display a high degree of subjectiveness.

That subjectiveness raises in turn the issue of the authors of such social artefacts: who selects those specific community features that are to become the backbone of those imaginaries? As a social construct, imaginaries are arguably the creation of hegemonic elites who decide on the content of the legacy, what to keep and what to forget, what to insist on and what to set aside. Collective imaginaries are the result of an enterprise conducted by a happy few who pretend to speak on behalf of an entire ‘We, the People’.

At the same time, however, collective imaginaries cannot be a sheer social construct devised by purely rational minds. Those elites are themselves influenced, at least unconsciously, by the groundswell constituted by those entrenched imaginaries inherited from the past. Although those elites shall certainly shape them and modify them, they also receive them as a given since those imaginaries are a part of their very autobiography. This bears a very important consequence regarding the possibility for an imaginary to be substituted by another: although an imaginary may certainly be redirected, it cannot arguably be entirely revamped. It is to be lasting.

Constitutional imaginaries as collective imaginaries

As specifically regards *constitutional* imaginaries, this paper adopts Jan Komárek’s proposed definition: ‘a set of ideas and beliefs that help to motivate and justify the practice of government and collective self-rule. Such imaginaries are as important as institutions and office holders formally embedded in constitutions. They provide political action (anchored in the constitution and getting expression through the medium of law) with an overarching sense and purpose recognized by

those governed as legitimate.⁴ Two aspects within constitutional imaginaries appear salient in this proposed definition: the foundational dimension and the unconsciousness dimension. It is in the light of each of these aspects that heuristic tools can be devised in order to determine the content of a given imaginary.

As far as the foundational element underpinning constitutional imaginaries is concerned, those imaginaries are characterised by their axiological importance for the building up and continued existence of a given political community. They confer democratic legitimacy and popular support on their political institutions by virtue of the supposedly deep adherence of the people to that imaginary. Digging into those foundations may be done with two main tools. First, intellectual history – as contextualised political thought⁵ - will allow to find out the various strands within the political thought and their respective weights in a given community, at a given time. It will especially allow to unearth continuity and rupture within political thought. Second, constitutional law arguably reflects constitutional imaginaries. It is thus opportune to examine the grand narratives contained in the preamble or first provisions of a constitution. A certain imaginary will also be reflected by the structure and content of a constitution, the constitutional arrangements provided for therein regarding the form of the state, the type of separation of powers, the balance of powers among political institutions, the degree of commitment towards fundamental rights achieved by the constitution and by constitutional jurisprudence.⁶

⁴ Jan Komárek, 'European Constitutional Imaginaries: Utopias, Ideologies and the Other', in Jan Komárek (ed.), *European Constitutional Imaginaries: Between Ideology and Utopia*, Oxford University Press, 2023, p. 2.

⁵ On the methods in intellectual history, see in particular Quentin Skinner, 'Meaning and Understanding in the History of Ideas' (1969) *History and Theory*, 8.

⁶ In France, the contribution of constitutional scholarship to the study on constitutional imaginaries has been unfortunately somewhat limited because of the dominant positivistic tradition that has downplayed constitutional history and philosophy. Apart from the notable exception of the Institut Michel Villey and its e-journal *Jus Politicum*, there is little interest into the study of constitutional law in context in France. Even there, it is usually done with a retrospective, learned interest in past authors, with limited attention to the political and social context within which those authors developed their thoughts and to what could be, *mutadis mutandis*, their contribution for the present times. See, however, for a proposal to look at the constitutions 'in their becoming', Denis Baranger, « Le piège du droit constitutionnel », *Jus Politicum*, n° 3, 2009, p. 13 (<http://juspoliticum.com/article/Le-piege-du-droit-constitutionnel-146.html>).

As regards the unconsciousness element, constitutional imaginaries are most of the time invisible.⁷ They are so deeply engrained in a given collective psyche that they sound like self-evident truths that are certainly hard to challenge but, above all, hard to identify in the first place. While looking at the foundations through intellectual history and constitutional law constitutes a way to unveil the content of those imaginaries, political events or moments are another heuristic tool to bring the invisible to the fore. Those events involving the people shall serve as confirmations of what the other two heuristic tools have led to discover as part of the content of constitutional imaginaries.

Let us call those moments *epiphanies* as those usually rare moments of ‘apparition’, when the heart of national imaginaries surface as the result of a tension, of a strain between an entrenched constitutional imaginary and competing ideologies or trends that undermine the former. Epiphanies consist in eruptive moments whereby the main features of a constitutional imaginary emerge as a society reaction to a countervailing movement. Epiphanies refer to those moments of collision between tectonic plates where the old narratives clash with new phenomena. Drawing on another metaphor, epiphanies are like precipitates in chemistry where the addition of a new substance to the invisible old mix suddenly reveals the nature and content of the latter.

2. The French constitutional imaginary as a Republican imaginary

French republicanism and Anglo-Saxon liberalism: a tale of two different liberal traditions

When looking at intellectual history, liberalism appears as a multifaceted concept. As Sir Larry Siedentop, a renowned specialist of French liberalism, explained in a

⁷ See eg Laurence H. Tribe, *The Invisible Constitution*, Oxford UP, 2018.

famous essay first published in 1979,⁸ there are at least two liberal traditions: the Anglo-Saxon tradition (the obvious one, so to speak, when thinking of liberalism) and the French tradition. Despite their common commitment to liberty, those two traditions stand in stark contrast with one another. While the former is premised on negative liberty, the second one rests on positive, civic or political liberty. It follows that French liberalism significantly differs from Anglo-Saxon liberalism. Their difference is so radical that, although formally correct, using the term liberalism for the French experience appears unsuitable.

Within the Anglo-Saxon scheme of thought, ever since John Locke at least, society prevails over the state and more generally over public authority. Accordingly, individuals enjoy rights that shall be enforced against the state. According to Locke, that entailed in the first place the absolute protection of the right to property as a condition for individual liberty. More generally, the Anglo-Saxon liberal tradition acknowledges the importance of individual rights, ranging from the free exercise of religious beliefs up to the right to non-discrimination. Within that tradition, far from being an instrument the aim of which is to fulfil the goals of the state, law shall protect individual emancipation from undue state interferences. Law thus serves as a limitation on state action in the name of the individual, of subjective rights, of liberal (or negative⁹) constitutionalism within a pluralistic society.

The French Republican tradition is totally at odds with such an approach.¹⁰ It primarily values political liberty. Where Anglo-Saxon liberalism focuses on the individual as both a starting point and an end in itself, Republicanism focuses on the abstract citizen. Where Anglo-Saxon liberalism is deprived of grand narratives,

⁸ Larry Siedentop, 'Two Liberal Traditions', in *The Idea of Freedom: Essays in Honour of Isaiah Berlin*, Oxford UP, 1979.

⁹ See Martin Loughlin, *op. cit.*, p. 8.

¹⁰ On French republicanism, see eg Claude Nicolet, *L'idée républicaine en France. Essai d'histoire critique (1789-1924)*, Tel Gallimard, 1995 ; Jean-Fabien Spitz, 'On the Supposed Illiberalism of Republican Political Culture in France', in Stephen W. Sawyer, Ian Stewart (eds.), *In Search of the Liberal Moment: Democracy, Anti-totalitarianism and Intellectual Politics in France since 1950*, New York, Plagrave, 2016, pp. 111-129.

collective mobilising stories pushing for voluntaristic, political action flourish within the Republican ethos. According to the Republican approach, the state is to shape society since what primarily matters within that model is not individual liberty, but the political liberty of (and as) ‘We the people’.

Under that voluntaristic tradition, the bottom line of the French political thought for centuries has indeed been the state (and more generally the public sphere), be it in economic, political, social or legal matters. From Louis 14th (“*l’Etat c’est moi*”) up to the present times, the state has played in France that mystical and omnipresent role as the sole source of legal authority entrusted with the noble mission of building the French citizen. While the Anglo-Saxon thought rests on a strict separation between public and private, that is between state and society, the French Republican tradition thus embraces a looser approach to that separation on the somewhat authoritarian premise that the state knows better what is good for society than society itself. The state does not therefore need in all circumstances the latter’s consent to decide and implement policies.

In that respect, the concept at the heart of the Republican culture is that of general interest or general will. Far from being the sum of individual interests within a pluralistic society (in a Smithian way), the general interest is presented as a transcending interest (in a Rousseauian way) that ultimately – and conveniently – allows state rulers to mould society at will.¹¹ It logically follows that, within that pattern, individual rights are not the paramount consideration. They will often be superseded by public interest.

It thus appears that the French and Anglo-Saxon ‘liberal’ traditions are radically different because they are themselves based on significantly different definitions of liberty. The French tradition is premised on collective liberty (positive, civic

¹¹ On the prevailing Rousseauian philosophy in French legal thought, in particular with regard to Europe, see Justine Lacroix, *La pensée française à l’épreuve de l’Europe*, Grasset, 2008; Céline Spector, « La “ voie rousseauiste ” et les impasses de la critique souverainiste de l’Union européenne », in Tristan Coignard, Céline Spector (dir.), *Europe philosophique, Europe politique. L’héritage des Lumières*, Classiques Garnier, 2022, pp.171-189.

liberty) where the state is the main, if not only, vector for realising such liberty. Such view has been the prevailing political thought over centuries in France. It dates back to the Enlightenment and the French (Jacobine) Revolution. It is even possible, with some minor stretching, to hold that that Republican thinking was already present in a specific form during the Ancient Regime. There are indeed key elements of continuity between the Republican thinking and the Ancient Regime: the state has always had a key role in the construction of France and the French people as a nation; and the general interest is ultimately the secular avatar of the Ancient Regime's common good.

Traces of the Republican imaginary within French constitutional law

Several traces of that Republican tradition can be spotted in French constitutional law. First of all, there has always been in France an unbridled passion for constitutions. Since 1791, France has had no fewer than fifteen constitutions when the United States have notoriously had only one. While the constitution that is currently in force in France bears the longevity record (65 years old), it has however itself been revised on numerous occasions.

One could assume that such constitutional frenzy suggests the adherence of the French people to the now widespread vision of constitutionalism as an individual-rights-based limit on state action (liberal or negative constitutionalism). Such a view is ill-conceived. The fact that the French appear so eager about constitutional change rather suggests adherence to a very different approach to constitutionalism that appears somewhat forgotten in learned discussions on constitutionalism nowadays, namely positive or political constitutionalism: the will to achieve the best political regime through constitutional arrangements.¹²

Such trust for constitutions as tools to establish an ideal regime is a noteworthy trait of the Republican thought. What matters is not the protection of the individual but the type of collective, political liberty and the most suitable balance

¹² See eg Olivier Beaud, 'L'histoire du concept de constitution en France. De la constitution politique à la constitution comme statut juridique de l'Etat', *Jus Politicum*, n° 3, 2009 (available at http://www.juspoliticum.com/uploads/pdf/JP3_beaud.pdf).

between the executive power and the legislative power. The key question within the Republican model is therefore not how to best safeguard individual liberty against public encroachments, but what is the suitable balance of powers to ensure political liberty (which was incidentally the only, albeit major, issue that a liberal philosopher such as Montesquieu himself was interested in).

In other words, the French have always been much more concerned with maximising political liberty through political institutions rather than with constraining the latter in order to maximise individual freedoms. When it comes to constitutionalism, French political thinkers – Sieyès in the first place – have accordingly privileged the view under which a constitution is the expression of the sovereign people’s absolute *pouvoir constituant* (constitution-making power) over that under which a constitution is a means for individuals to be protected against the sovereign people.¹³

Second, the pervasiveness of Republicanism throughout French constitutions lies in those grand narratives and principles that are usually mentioned in the preamble or the very first provisions of a constitution. Most French constitutions up to the present times have begun with the mention of France as one and indivisible.¹⁴ Such statements are certainly illustrative of the significance of the centralisation of power in Paris. They are also indicative of the indivisible character of sovereignty and of the general will in France: one people, one power, one state. Indivisibility has precluded until now any evolution of France towards a federal form of the state or any recognition of another people within France but the French people.¹⁵

Third, in accordance with the conception under which the public interest (under the label ‘general interest’ or ‘general will’) is paramount in France, the French

¹³ See eg Martin Loughlin, Neil Walker (eds.), *The Paradox of Constitutionalism. Constituent Power and Constitutional Form*, Oxford University Press, 2008.

¹⁴ See for instance the first sentence of Article 1 of the 1958 Constitution: ‘France shall be an indivisible, secular, democratic and social Republic’.

¹⁵ See decision n° 91-290 of Conseil constitutionnel of 9th May 1991, that refused to admit the existence of the ‘Corsica people’.

republican imaginary has not been primarily concerned with individual rights. The traditional precedence of the general interest over rights has taken different forms in French law, ranging from the – relative – absence of review mechanisms designed to enforce individual rights against state organs to a hegemonic parliament that could adopt any law in the name of the general will that the former had a monopoly to represent and flesh out. Such priority granted to the general interest has also taken the form of a limited protection of certain individual rights on account of the sacrosanct general will. Up to the present days, the right to non-discrimination has been interpreted in a restrictive manner in France. Unlike in those jurisdictions where different situations must be treated differently, in France different situations may be treated in the same way if the general interest mandates it.¹⁶ Within the Republican pattern, individuals are indeed still primarily seen as abstract citizens, not as individuals with their specific features. Individuals are worth of consideration only to the extent that they contribute to political liberty as active citizens.

By the same token, the Republican model also finds its expression in the curtailed freedom of religion.¹⁷ As is well-known, France is characterised by a strong commitment towards the hardly translatable term of *laïcité* and French courts have been adamant regarding in particular the wearing of the Islamic veil in schools or other public services.¹⁸ Although that exception has until now been upheld by the ECtHR under the margin of appreciation doctrine, it arguably constitutes a significant, perhaps even disproportionate, restriction to freedom of religion.

Likewise and in stark contrast with Locke's view, private property has been far from being central within the Republican thought.¹⁹ During the French

¹⁶ See for example judgment of the French Conseil d'Etat of 29th March 1997, *Société Baxter*, case n° 179049.

¹⁷ See Cécile Laborde, *Critical Republicanism: The Hijab Controversy and Political Philosophy*, Oxford University Press, 2012.

¹⁸ See for instance judgment of the French Conseil d'Etat of 2 Novembre 1992, *Kherouaa*, case n° 130394.

¹⁹ See Jean-Fabien Spitz, *op. cit.*, pp. 114-117.

Revolution, Robespierre clearly expressed his doubts regarding private property and explained that it was supposed to yield to the right to exist and live as human beings. Still nowadays, there is a significant fringe of the population and of political parties or trade unions that believe in collective property, demonise private property and defend public property of network industries. In such context, there is therefore little wonder why a significant body of legal rules (known as ‘droit administratif des biens’) aims at protecting public property in France.

Of course, it would be erroneous to think that fundamental rights were not protected at all in France until recent times. However, they have remained more secondary compared to other European countries. Most interestingly, the first fundamental rights that have been safeguarded in France are not individual rights, but collective, public freedoms (*libertés publiques*), that is those rights (such as freedom of the press, freedom of reunion, freedom of association) that fosters that very political liberty central to the Republican ethos. The modus operandi whereby those freedoms have been protected is equally interesting : they have been laid down by Parliament, not by courts, which is again illustrative of the fact that it is considered the task of political institutions (as opposed to judicial organs) to realise political liberty by putting forward such freedoms.

As a fourth and last illustration of the pervasiveness of the Republican imaginary in French law, it appears necessary to insist on that specific branch of public law that has emerged in the wake of the French revolution and which is both envied and looked at with suspicion, if not horror, by those who embrace the Anglo-Saxon approach to liberty. Despite the French passion for constitutions, constitutional law is certainly not the most prestigious discipline within public law. The most noble branch is administrative law. The very existence in France of *ad hoc* administrative courts (for a long time the sole Conseil d’Etat) to adjudicate on disputes involving state organs and the gradual definition by that Conseil d’Etat of a corpus of special, derogatory rules favourable to the public interest is itself revealing.

Together with the *summa divisio* within French academia between public law professors and private law professors, administrative law attests to the special status of public authorities that, at least in theory, are entrusted with the eminent task of implementing legislative choices made by Parliament in the name of Rousseau's general interest. In particular, in the wake of Léon Duguit, a famous administrative lawyer from the early 20th century, administrative law was meant to provide a framework for the state to deliver various public services with an explicit solidarity aim inspired by Emile Durkheim. The objective of ensuring social interdependence between individuals justified the derogatory character of those rules and the unilateral enforcement privilege enjoyed by executive organs of the state, with no need for the consent of individual addressees of administrative measures.

Are French liberal authors liberals?

Against that strong Republican background, France has often been criticised or mocked for what appears to be an illiberal political culture when liberalism is defined in Anglo-Saxon terms (see for example Hayek or Pierre Rosanvallon). The claim is that France could never convert to a liberal culture that would value private property, entrepreneurship and individual rights. That is perhaps true. However, it would be not only caricatural but wrong to take the view that there has never been any liberal authors in France so that the Anglo-Saxon, individualist approach to liberalism would be entirely foreign to the French political thought.²⁰

Admittedly, purely liberal authors are scarce and little known or studied. Frédéric Bastiat or Jacques Rueff, who believed first and foremost in individuals and entrepreneurship and wished to limit state interference within economics, politics and society, have always been marginal in France. Even someone like Raymond

²⁰ For a comprehensive approach on French liberals ever since the Enlightenment, Raf Geenens, Helena Rosenblatt (eds.), *French Liberalism from Montesquieu to the Present Day*, Cambridge UP, 2012. See especially the editors' introduction 'French liberalism, an overlooked tradition?', pp. 1-12.

Aron,²¹ despite all his intellectual prominence in the seventies, seems to have been forgotten, as if his own liberal legacy did not matter much in Republican France.

There are however several names who are usually associated with an individualistic, Anglo-Saxon approach to liberty: Montesquieu in the 18th century, Benjamin Constant, Alexis de Tocqueville or Guizot in the 19th century and, more recently Claude Lefort, Marcel Gauchet or Pierre Manent. Arguably, however, all those thinkers have developed a non-conventional liberal approach that combines what has been described above as the two liberal traditions. Those authors have indeed endorsed a refined political thought that does not conform to Anglo-Saxon liberalism but rather reaches a unique, distinctively French mix between political liberty and civil liberties.

Starting with early French liberals, Montesquieu developed more a theory of moderation than a liberal theory and his '*doux commerce*' theory is not as favourable to free trade and globalisation as one may think.²² He was also primarily concerned with the separation of powers, that is ensuring that no political institution would abuse its own power at the expense of another institution. Montesquieu appeared less interested in how power could negatively affect individual rights. It is also well-known that he did not have high trust in courts of law and only saw in judges the mere 'mouths of the law'.

By the same token, even among those authors that have advocated in favour of individual rights, be it Constant or Tocqueville, neither of them has embraced a one-sided conception of freedom.²³ Their works displayed an equal insistence on political liberty. In particular, in its famous *Discours de l'Athénée*,²⁴ Constant expressly distinguished between *liberty of the Ancients* (in essence, the Republican

²¹ See eg Aurelian Craiutu, 'Raymond Aron and the tradition of political moderation in France', in Raf Geenens, Helena Rosenblatt (eds.), *op. cit.*, pp. 271-290.

²² Céline Spector, 'Was Montesquieu liberal? The Spirit of the Law in the history of liberalism', in Raf Geenens, Helena Rosenblatt (eds.), *op. cit.*, pp. 57-72.

²³ Andrew Jainchill, 'The importance of Republican liberty in French liberalism', in Raf Geenens, Helena Rosenblatt (eds.), *op. cit.*, pp. 73-89.

²⁴ Benjamin Constant, 'De la liberté des anciens comparée à celle des modernes', in *Ecrits politiques*, Gallimard, 1997, 2nd edition, p. 618.

freedom) and *liberty of the Moderns* (in essence, Anglo-Saxon liberty), but considered that both were important and should therefore be valued. For its part, a statesman such as Guizot in 1830 that is usually presented as a liberal did not hesitate to implement state-based policies. Guizot thus equally proved Republican in his approach to the extent that his economic liberalism appeared somewhat authoritarian, top-down and definitely state-friendly as opposed to being purely market-based.²⁵

As far as more recent liberal authors are concerned, their commitment towards liberalism appears equally dubious, and by all means contingent. As is well-known, France offered a vibrant intellectual scene in the seventies. That time was not only characterized by libertarian aspirations but also by the discovery of the crimes committed in the name of communism, especially in the wake of the publication of Solzhenitsyn's writings. Several authors who used to be at least sympathetic towards communism changed under what was usually called the liberal turn of the seventies,²⁶ when Constant or Tocqueville, who had fallen into oblivion, were rediscovered.²⁷ That is the case of François Furet but also of Claude Lefort or Marcel Gauchet who started embracing the cause of individual rights protection.²⁸ However, before being liberal, the liberal turn was actually anti-totalitarian or at least antifascist. Philosophers such as Lefort and Gauchet started to embrace liberalism but it would be wrong to see in the evaluation of their political thought a conversion to Anglo-Saxon liberalism, especially on the part of Lefort who actually had limited interest into subjective rights. Instead of coming up with a theory on the limitation of power (negative constitutionalism), Lefort came up with

²⁵ See Lucien Jaume, 'The unity, diversity and paradoxes of French liberalism', in Raf Geenens, Helena Rosenblatt (eds.), *op. cit.*, pp. 36-54.

²⁶ On that liberal turn in French political thought, see especially Stephen W. Sawyer, Iain Stewart, 'Introduction: New Perspectives on France's "Liberal moment"', in Stephen W. Sawyer, Iain Stewart (eds), *op. cit.*, pp. 11-16.

²⁷ For a collection of the main articles dedicated to Tocqueville written by various authors in the seventies or eighties, see Laurence Guellec (dir.), *Tocqueville et l'esprit de la démocratie*, Presses de Sciences Po, 2005.

²⁸ See eg Samuel Moyn, 'The Politics of individual rights: Marcel Gauchet and Claude Lefort', in R. Geenens, H. Rosenblatt, *op. cit.*, pp. 291-310; Noah Rosenblum, 'Rethinking the French Liberal Moment: Some Thoughts on the Heterogeneous Origins of Lefort and Gauchet's Social Philosophy', in Stephen W. Sawyer, Iain Stewart (eds), *op. cit.*, pp. 61-83.

a theory of political regimes and democracy, illustrating yet again that French interest in the ideal type of political regime (positive constitutionalism). He developed on that occasion a theory of *political* rights which assumed the ‘situatedness’ of human beings as a legacy, in Lefort’s case, of both Republicanism and Marxism. By the same token, Pierre Manent or Marcel Gauchet have embraced Tocqueville and Aron. At the same time, they remained deeply indebted to the Republican thought, as illustrated both by their strong critique of the ‘human rights ideology’ and by their conviction that democracy could not be achieved outside the political framework of the nation-state.

Thus, it is highly debatable whether, *intellectually*, France went through a liberal turn in the seventies. It seems almost impossible for French thinkers to embrace with resolve Anglo-Saxon liberalism precisely because of that entrenched Republican imaginary, especially when that latter was combined with a Marxist ideology. Back in the seventies already, it was considered more appropriate ‘to be wrong with Sartre [the communist] than right with Aron [the liberal]’, French intellectual elites’ affinity with Marxism being the ultimate offspring of Republicanism stretched to its outer limits. Today, the situation has not drastically changed. Robespierre and Sartre are still alive while Raymond Aron is off radar.

By the same token, the entrenched Republican imaginary in France seems to make it almost impossible to think of Europe in a ‘non-French’, that is in a ‘non-Republican’ way. As a consequence, not only is it hard to grasp an idea such as federalism, the latter being arguably not a part of the French hardware, but there is also a tendency to conceptualise the European Union as a bigger, centralised France, thus on the basis of French political concepts such as sovereignty,²⁹ the Republic,³⁰ or the state. As regards the latter, it is striking, as Lacroix pointed out, that the issue of the nature of European integration is still discussed nowadays in French scholarship in institutional terms (is the EU a (federal) state or a mere

²⁹ See Emmanuel Macron’s speech on Europe in September 2017 at the Sorbonne.

³⁰ See eg Philippe Crignon, ‘De l’Europe républicaine à la République européenne’, in Tristan Coignard, Céline Spector (dir.), *Europe philosophique, Europe politique*, Classiques Garnier, 2022, pp. 75-103.

international organization?), as if it was simply impossible for a French mind to think of European integration outside an *institutional* framework.³¹

3. The liberal turn of French constitutional law

French intellectual history thus appears out of tune with the specific developments that France has gone through ever since the seventies. While the ‘liberal turn’ of the seventies *within political thought* is ambiguous in its meaning and motivations, it remains that the French Republican imaginary has been specifically shaken up from the seventies by major political and legal transformations largely induced by (Anglo-Saxon) liberal tremors under the influence of external factors such as globalisation, belonging to the EU and the ECHR system, the rise of rule of law considerations together with the protection of individual rights and the correlative distrust towards a transcendental approach to the general interest and what can be done in its name.

Although those factors have not provoked a shift in the political thought (but have at least triggered resistance and discussion among political philosophers), they have pushed or at least supported significant changes in the theory and practice of French law, especially constitutional law. That liberal turn in the law has materialised in at least two ways: first, those various factors have put to the test several key concepts that have been at the crossroads between French constitutional law and the Republican political thought; second, they have fostered the Anglo-Saxon version of liberalism, economically through neoliberalism and politically through liberal constitutionalism.

First, the demise (or at least transformation) of the traditional concepts of constitutional law can be witnessed. As explained by Denis Baranger, ‘the key concepts of constitutional law are leaving the stage. That withdrawal takes the form of a gradual loss of meaning. The words are still used but one does no longer

³¹ See Justine Lacroix, *La pensée française à l'épreuve de l'Europe*, Grasset, 2008, p. 14.

know what they mean'.³² For instance, while the figure of the (abstract) citizen was central in the Republican ethos and notably found its specific legal expression in the case-law on equality, the concept of citizenship is often used nowadays as a mere vague adjective. Where it is used as a noun, like in EU law, it refers to citizens who enjoy substantive rights within a conception of freedom as individual emancipation, not as civic participation to the general interest of society. A similar transformation has affected the concept of constitution. That concept is increasingly replaced by that of constitutionalism understood as liberal or negative constitutionalism. Nowadays, constitutions are increasingly seen, including in France, as an instrument to limit public power, not mainly an instrument to devise the best and most suitable political regime. That explains the more and more frequent paradox whereby a constitution can be deemed... unconstitutional.

By the same token, the concept of sovereignty, which has been salient in France since the emergence of the modern state, does no longer appear intelligible or useful to understand state power while it used to be a defining element of the latter. The traditional meaning of sovereignty is at odds with liberal constitutionalism. Even when bestowed upon the people and not the king, it still refers to the idea of an absolute, unitary and indivisible power that is intrinsically incompatible with the idea of limitation of power underpinning liberal constitutionalism. Moreover, its meaning has become diluted because of the variety of its uses. Sometimes, (state) sovereignty is said to be pooled or shared (but is it still 'sovereignty' once the classic concept has been stripped of its constitutive element?). Sometimes, sovereignty is just discarded for its being no longer a fully operative concept to describe those nation states that have now become member states. It is then replaced by another discourse, that of 'constitutional identity', which appears to be a pale substitute of a bygone sovereignty. Sometimes again, if no longer used in relation to the states, the word sovereignty is simply used in relation to the European Union to suggest some kind of strategic autonomy vis-à-vis other regions of the world.

³² Denis Baranger, *op. cit.*, p. 19 (free translation).

Second, the major transformation of constitutional law that has been prompted by the liberal turn from the seventies onwards is the result of the constant rise of fundamental rights protection and rule of law considerations. In France, there used to be no review of legislation (and hardly of administrative measures) with regard to individual rights. Three reasons may explain that legal vacuum: the primary role initially assigned to the French constitutional court by the Constitution of 1958 currently in force was to enforce the separation of powers, not fundamental rights; the Constitution did not enumerate fundamental rights nor contained a bill of rights among its first provisions; parliamentary sovereignty (the so-called *légicentrisme*, that is the intangible character of acts adopted by parliament) together with distrust towards courts have been material to the Republican tradition and have long precluded judicial review of legislation.

It is in 1971 that liberal constitutionalism has significantly pervaded French constitutional law in a seminal judgment of the Conseil constitutionnel (the French *Marbury v Madison* so to speak) whereby the constitutional court has for the first time struck down a parliamentary bill for a breach of a fundamental right (or rather ‘public liberty’ in French parlance), namely freedom of association.³³ Despite that major change, the Conseil constitutionnel was still not entitled to review parliamentary acts after their enactment. Once in force, parliamentary acts could not be challenged on constitutionality grounds. It is only four decades later that France revised its constitution and provided for a constitutional adjudication procedure allowing the Conseil constitutionnel to carry out *ex post* review of acts of parliament (the now famous ‘QPC’, standing for *question prioritaire de constitutionnalité*).

However, the rise of liberal constitutionalism in the seventies and eighties is primarily the result of external factors, namely EU integration and the ECHR. French ordinary courts have indeed gradually accepted to enforce international and above all European treaties and acts adopted on the basis of the latter against

³³ See François-Xavier Millet, *L'Union européenne et l'identité constitutionnelle des Etats membres*, LGDJ-Lextenso, 2012, pp. 8-9 and pp. 299-306.

French acts of parliament.³⁴ Such Copernican revolution prompted from outside France significantly undermined the French Republican imaginary in at least two ways: first, that transformation empowered non-democratically-elected courts to the expense of democratically-elected institutions, Parliament in the first place; second, such transformation did not only entail that nation-states were not the only source of law and power but that legal norms created outside the state could prevail over state law. Accordingly, ever since the seventies, the Republican imaginary has been constantly undermined through a phenomenon of legal acculturation to liberal constitutionalism.

4. Epiphanies of the Republican imaginary in reaction to Anglo-Saxon liberalism

That the French Republican imaginary is being insidiously shaken up by the rise of Anglo-Saxon liberalism is finally demonstrated also by political acts of resistance or contestation that highlight the tensions within French society between the entrenched Republican imaginary and the pervasiveness of Anglo-Saxon liberalism. As previously explained, epiphanies are those moments full of dramatic intensity where various competing strands of thought, *in casu* the Republican tradition and the liberal thought, frontally clash, thereby confirming the core Republican content of the French constitutional imaginary.

Interestingly, those moments have always concerned debates closely or remotely relating to Europe. That is not surprising inasmuch as the latter tests the very Republican concepts and political thought.³⁵ EU integration as a regional embodiment and experiment of globalisation has carried with it values different from those characteristic of the Republican thought. Not only does the EU's

³⁴ See Daniel Halberstam, 'How Europe Brought Judicial Review to France: A Response to Bruce Ackerman', in Richard Albert (ed.), *Revolutionary Constitutionalism: Law, Legitimacy, Power*, Hart Publishing, 2020, pp. 239-264.

³⁵ See Justine Lacroix, *op. cit.* ; Céline Spector, *No Demos? Souveraineté et démocratie à l'épreuve de l'Europe*, Seuil, 2021.

existence suggest that there can be legitimate law (and even constitutionalism) beyond the nation-state, but the EU itself was founded on neoliberal premises that praise the market and competition and limit state interferences in the economy. The EU has gradually also embarked on the liberal constitutionalism ship to such an extent that the Court of Justice has recently taken the view that the protection of individual rights and the rule of law are part and parcel of no less than the EU's own constitutional identity.³⁶

Three epiphanies are illustrative of the tectonic tension between the French Republican imaginary and the Anglo-Saxon imaginary diffused by European integration and globalisation: the referendum on the Maastricht Treaty in 1992, the referendum on the European Constitution in 2005 and the Yellow Vests movement.

First, the referendum on the ratification of the Maastricht Treaty in 1992, which was narrowly won by the 'Yes' side, shed light on a split within French society between what French philosopher Régis Debray called the 'nationaux-républicains' and the 'libéraux-libertaires'.³⁷ That terminology is revealing in itself since it opposes, on the one hand, the Republican thought, which is attached to the nation-states and to the concepts of Republicanism and, on the other hand, the liberal thought that focuses on individual freedoms.

Second, the referendum on the ratification of the European Constitution in 2005 opposed the two same groups. However, another divide along economic lines also appeared within French society between those in favour of a 'social Europe' and those in favour of a 'neoliberal Europe'. Although that second divide did not correspond to the earlier one but cut across it, it suggests that there is also another type of opposition prompted by EU integration, this time between neo-liberals and those that adhere to the solidarity component of the Republican ideal.

³⁶ CJEU, Case C-156/21, judgment of 16 February 2021, *Hungary v. European Parliament and Council*, para. 232.

³⁷ Régis Debray, *Le Code et le Glaive. Après l'Europe, la Nation ?*, Albin Michel, 2016.

Finally, although the Yellow Vests movement in 2018/2019 was not directly born from a public discussion on Europe, it largely overlapped with the pro-Maastricht and the anti-Maastricht divide, between those that make gains out of globalisation and those do not.

In all three events, the lurking Republican tradition abruptly erupted to the surface in the context of liberal threats for its integrity. Although it is hard to know whether all three epiphanies show a persistently strong, albeit rather unconscious, adherence of the French people to the Republican thought as a whole or merely to certain of its dimensions (such as solidarity), they all highlight a rejection of Anglo-Saxon liberalism by a significant chunk of the population.

Conclusion

In order to unearth the content of the French constitutional imaginary, I have started with providing a method to that effect. I have proposed to examine the grand narratives and key concepts as they notably derive from French intellectual history and constitutional law. I have also suggested to look at epiphanies, that is salient political events in times of crisis, for a confirmation of the content of constitutional imaginaries, where tectonic tensions between opposing ideologies come to the fore within public discussion.

I have shown that the French Republican imaginary is essentially different from Anglo-Saxon liberalism, primarily on account of the importance assigned to political liberty and to constitutions as instruments that enable to realise that type of liberty through the search of the ideal political regime. The French Republican imaginary permeates French constitutional law. It is what explains the latter's key concepts, the adherence to the political approach to constitutions and the French passion for constitutions to fulfil political liberty.

Political liberty, the underlying vision of society and the role of political institutions in shaping society have been the red thread that has been running through the French political thought and legal practice for decades. The Republican imaginary is so strong that a great deal of French authors who are usually portrayed as liberals, Montesquieu included, have in fact endorsed a conception of liberalism that differs from Anglo-Saxon authors by combining political liberty and civil liberties.

The rise of Anglo-Saxon liberalism in the Western world from the seventies onwards has created fertile ground for a destabilisation of the French Republican tradition. The latter is being shaken up by the vehicles of Anglo-Saxon liberalism, such as the European Union and the system established by the European Convention on Human Rights, which have promoted individualism and strengthened fundamental rights and rule of law considerations to the detriment of the general will. Those vehicles have triggered major, insidious changes in the law through the demise or semantic transformation of the grand Republican narratives and concepts and the emergence of new *modus operandi* and procedures.

Although legal practices have significantly changed over the past fifty years, French political philosophers and, a fortiori, the people themselves seem to remain attached to the Republican imaginary. The rise of Anglo-Saxon liberalism in Europe has not translated yet into a new corpus of political thought (nor into a significantly ‘new people’) that would clearly privilege civil liberties.

Intellectuals appear so much imbued with general-interest-based Republican thinking that it appears virtually impossible to fully embrace in France a different approach to liberty, as if intellectuals were captive of their own context, as if the Republican values were so deeply rooted in the collective psyche in France that it is impossible to significantly depart from it and embrace a new intellectual path. It is striking, from intellectuals who should precisely be totally insulated from their own autobiography so to speak, be it individual or collective, that French

liberal authors have never theorized liberalism until its ultimate boundaries but have bounced back to some Republican ideals. It is equally striking that ‘non-Republicans’ politically speaking (that is monarchists or bonapartists) have as well embraced the view of an overriding general interest, which is so central in the Republican thought.³⁸ Of course, different contents are then assigned to the general interest by those ‘non-Republicans’. Yet what unites all of them is the concept and function of an overhanging general will that justifies limits to individual action and empowers the state in shaping society: the ‘Res Publica’.

Accordingly, there seems to be no proper escape from the Republican tradition in one form or another and that it is simply impossible to be ‘properly’ liberal in France. At best, the Republican tradition could adopt a slightly new shape under the sway of liberalism. It is probably what it is already going through now. However, it is doubtful that Republicanism and liberalism can ever be reconciled since their respective premises, albeit both formally liberal, are far too different.

³⁸ Spitz has shown that bonapartisme is not far away from the Republican culture, nor from the Ancient Regime (Jean-Fabien Spitz, ‘On the Supposed Illiberalism of Republican Political Culture in France’, in Sawyer, Stewart (eds), *op. cit.*, p. 111, at 113).